

RAINWATER ELECTROLYSIS USING AUTOMOTIVE TRUCK

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ABSTRACT

Many people face a lot of issues when they go out during rain time. Many solutions exist for this issue, such as sending a truck to suck these water stack on roads and streets, but it takes time and effort without community benefit. We believe we have a better solution to that, and it is by using Automotive truck electrolysis of rainwater which will produce two gases, Hydrogen and Oxygen. We believe this could be the best solution as it would ensure the industrial and hospitals will find suppliers affordable and local factory that is selling them the need it gases.

INTRODUCTION

Rain water can sometime become a major hazard to people and help can take time and sometimes it can be too late. Our project is a Automotive truck electrolysis of rainwater. We first came across this idea in our normal lives during the rainy season, we noticed that the traffic caused by the rain impacts the time management of many people, not to mention the safety issues it causes, therefor we kept thinking of a way to eliminate the problems and that how we came up with the idea. We spoke with people about this problem to expand our understanding of it and what we found out was helpful to a great extent. We found out by talk to the people, the areas most affected and how much of their time is consumed by the cluttered rainwater, which help us understand our target better.

VISION:

Our vision is to have a future where rainwater does not become an issue to people who wants to get to their jobs and drowned streets become something from the past, and our second goal is to have a profitable business model in the industry that not only benefit us as a business but benefits the community.

MISSION

Our mission is a green future with no harmful emissions and a business that benefits the community and the environment. We will draw the rainwater from roads and pavements to tanks which is going to be processed by a method called electrolysis. It will heat the rainwater to certain temperature and turn them into hydrogen and oxygen gases. This will help to supply our stakeholders who are hospitals, industries, airports etc.

Q5

Customize Save as

1. Did your car breakdown or you see others cars stop (breakdown) inroads during rain times?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

VALUES:

- High quality
- Fast
- Environment sensibility
- Community service
- Integrity

Q4

Customize Save as

1. How long does the rain water stay in roads?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

Q3

Customize Save as

1. Is there a need for new ways to get rid of the cluttered rain water ?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

GENERATING IDEAS

After we identified the problem, we needed to find a solution that befits the community and a rewarding model for us. We used the brain storming method so we can get different perspectives from all the group members and that helped us mix and match ideas until we came up with a convincing model. Then we did the why analysis to help us understand why we are doing the project and know what we are targeting with our innovation therefor, the ideas we came up with were consistent with the problem we are tackling.

APPROACH TO INNOVATION

After we got our ideas in line, we came up with ways to innovate the project by implementing new ways to deal with the problem we are facing. One of the ways we came up is making use of the rainwater we are collecting, by transferring the water to oxygen and hydrogen and selling it to the industry area which will benefit the industry and will benefit our business in a sustainable way.

LIMITATIONS

Our innovation faces some limitations that are not impossible to overcome. One of the limitations we are facing is getting the approval from the government to deploy our trucks in the streets and getting the permission to use that water that the trucks collect and transfer it to gas. Another limitation is the need for a financial support to get the innovation starting and that could be granted with the support of the government.

MARKET ANALYSIS

Addressing the market of our project is industry environment. It focuses on the rainwater drowning the streets and sideways of the streets (where people mostly walk). The reason of our project attraction is the solution of drowning streets and avoid cars being breakdown in middle of the streets. Finding out how does rainwater affecting the streets and cars from being in harmful heavy rainwater. Unfortunately, in our country, they just suck the heavy rainwater of the sidewalks and streets and not turning into useful resources. There is a big of view of returning of revenue in this industry and will achieve a big amount of investment. Comparing between our project and the sucking of rainwater is a huge difference. Our project will suck the rainwater and turn into useful resource.

CUSTOMERS AND CUSTOMER DEVELOPMENT

The target customers will focus on stuff that they ran of it quickly. Most likely, for our project, we focus on the customers who are looking for resources that are missing. The reason why the customer looking for this resource is using in different variation of industry like iron or hospital facilities. Nowadays, customers are scaling the quality of the material especially when comes to type of gases. Although, they are not looking into expensive with low quality that affects their projects. They are looking into good quality that is worth paying for it. Reason of using it results in excellent shape and easy to maintain the variances of the item. To reach into someone, we must communicate to them for our product and how is it going.

COMPETITION AND POSITIONING

Serving the customer by depending on the role of customer to have an equal mind of knowledge and thinking. It will be an employee unless the customer requests a high role person in our project. Mostly will CEO or VPs be requesting weekly or monthly check on our work if the business expands into big investment. One weakness we are facing is that there are many regulations we need to go through to approve our innovation and that should take some time to get. And the second challenge is that there are many competitions in the industry area that provide the same product however, we believe that our innovation is new and there is no one like us that has such a creative way to get the supply to meet the demand. Our project market shares and serve a high chance of stakeholders to cut of companies' demand. The major of this project will be growing or steady because if someone try to duplicate the project in different way, they might achieve their goal and make us decline. The obstacles are going to be the materials of the projects and it could be difficulty to find. Comparing to other competitors projects could be a barrier of someone else. Starting up helping from allies for spreading the project into social and sponsors. It could be getting little of budget from any surrounding friends or family for assisting us into a big project.

SWOT

OPPORTUNITY:

There is an opportunity in this innovation to give back to the community in a way that benefits both parties. Disposing of the stuck rainwater could help immensely in time management and safety, at the same time, taking the water we collect and converting it to oxygen and hydrogen and providing it to the industry could be very beneficial and sustainable.

WEAKNESS:

One weakness we are facing is that there are many regulations we need to go through to approve our innovation and that should take some time to get.

And the second challenge is that there are many competitions in the industry area that provide the same product however, we believe that our innovation is new and there is no one like us that has such a creative way to get the supply to meet the demand.

STRENGTH:

The strengths of our invention are that many places get drowning during rain time, and we can take benefit of them by separating oxygen and hydrogen and using them in many fields such as factories and hospitals.

THREAT:

Among the threats that we may face may be outside our control, an example of that is the lack of rain, the closure of the street, the inability of the truck to reach the site, the high-water level where the truck is unable to move.

How to use the strength to over the threat? The strengths of our invention are that many places get drowning during rain time, and we can take benefit of them by separating oxygen and hydrogen to over the threat, we will be able to use seawater instead of rainwater in usual time.

How to use the opportunities to over the weakness? Our weakness is the approval we need from the government, but we will serve the community and government services so we can be able to manage them.

BUSINESS MODEL AND LEAN STARTUP PHILOSOPHY

After discussing about the project, we are going to make it, we will start up with sponsors and stakeholders for advertising our business to be known in country. We will put a limit budget as beginning start of the project until we slightly increase the product and merge the sells with the stakeholders to until improving the project in small measurement of supplies and resources. Major risks could be in two situations market or technical. Market could be a limit season or specific season for this project. Mainly focusing on winter season. Technical issue could be from pumping or transferring energy from one source to the other and we must have plans or options to fix it immediately. Things we need to test is making a prototype of project and check the components if something missing or broken. Just a period to check our things before going into serious situations.

Starting					mid of year				
1x					2x				
Number of items	Name of item	Amount	Price	Total	Number of items	Name of item	Amount	Price	Total
1	Battery 12V	1	100	100	1	Battery 12V	2	100	200
2	Cylinder (11kg)	2	85	170	2	Cylinder (11kg)	4	85	340
3	Truck Tank	1	20,000	20000	3	Truck Tank	2	20,000	40000
4	Air Compressor	2	150	300	4	Air Compressor	4	150	600
5	Lead	2	100	200	5	Lead	4	100	400
Total Price		-	-	20770	Total Price		-	-	41540
Additional		-	-	-	Additional		-	-	-
Promoting		-	-	10,000	Promoting		4	10000	40,000
Other		-	-	2,000	Other		5	2000	10,000
End price		-	-	32770	End price		-	-	91540

End of year					
5x					
Number of items	Name of item	Amount	Price	Total	
1	Battery 12V	5	100	500	
2	Cylinder (11kg)	10	85	850	
3	Truck Tank	5	20,000	100000	
4	Air Compressor	10	150	1500	
5	Lead	10	100	1000	
Total Price		-	-	103850	
Additional		-	-	-	
Promoting		-	5	10000	50,000
Other		-	10	2000	20,000
End price		-	-	173850	

CONCLUSION

What we learnt is we had to put options of what ideas we have and search for it as first step. The group discuss the options were given and took one of them. In meanwhile, we change our project due to the situation where we going through was tough. So, we chose option b which is our project automotive truck electrolysis of rainwater. Our first draft of the project is collecting data from internet and researching for stakeholders and which market do we involve into. In between, we achieved 3rd which was honour and proud to start with our project like this. This idea has good choice in different ways of using it. It is true opportunity.

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